

Einstein Triumph over QM – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the recent developments in theoretical physics, and in particular the approach of starting with the equivalence principle of Gravity and acceleration, and using it to derive the coupling series as was done in the 8T, it is possible to validate that Einstein approach was right. That is in contrast to the modern approach taken by physicists, starting with QM and trying to derive gravity onto the theory.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. The 8T starts with Einstein theory of general relativity, it validates Einstein idea in less than half of a page, and only two previous equations were presented to reach that idea of equivalence between gravity and acceleration.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2}$$

Since we used calculus of variations and not tensor calculus, it is a somewhat different from Einstein theory. The main advantage of the calculus of variations is the vanishing of curvature as given by (1.48), which implies flatness, when we insert manifolds onto the EL operator. When we analyze the approach to a final theory, Einstein approach was right. It is much easier to start with gravity and derive the rest of the forces than to take the opposite root as taken by almost all physicists, starting with QM and trying to merge the Quantum gravity. Einstein was right in another sense, when he claimed that QM is not complete. QM described at the time only part of the terms in the coupling series, the strong and the electric, not even the weak interaction let alone the rest of the new interactions. In contrast to what is believed that Einstein left the frontier of physics after the development of QM it seems as his innate ideas and mindset were in fact correct. As Dirac once stated: "he always asked: If I was god, was I making the word like this? And according to the answer he would decide whether he liked a particular theory or not". In other words, an approach oriented to a search of beauty and simplicity, the same beauty and simplicity radiate from the primorial, and again validate the main point of this article, the great Einstein was right again, nature's nature is manifested in equations of great mathematical beauty and power. Which is also the simplest ideas we can conceive.

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.43)$$

Of course, the fact Einstein mindsets about nature were right, does not mean 8T and GR are the same. As was analyzed in previous papers, Einstein theory associate curvature of the metric tensor to fermion distributions while 8T regard those as ignorable variables by (1.48), Bosonic particles such as photons are responsible for the curvature, supported by the primordial coupling series, and therefore to space-time bending. It is also predicting that light is mediating the gravitational interaction as it is associated with the term (1.49) and has spin one, synonymous with long range, while gravitons have spin two, synonymous with short range. Einstein theory does not include the Quantum trait of spin, or any Quantum scale interactions and 8T predicts and includes all, in just one series. As Einstein once said about Newtown that a man of his time, he read nature with ease, we can say the same thing about the Great man, that he read nature with ease, that his intuition about a final theory was again right.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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